

Supplementary Information

Electrochemical Sensors for Cortisol: A Review

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Table S1: Definition of key sensor parameters and characteristics

Sensor characteristic	Definition/ description
Biological receptor/probe	The biorecognition element for the specific recognition and capture of the target analyte
Limit of detection	The lowest concentration of the target analyte likely to be reliably distinguished from the limit of blank (the highest apparent concentration of the target analyte expected to be found when replicates of a blank sample are tested) ¹
Dynamic range (also known as the quantification range ²)	The range of concentrations that expresses a concentration-response relationship, including the highest and lowest amount of analyte that can be reproducibly and reliably quantified with accuracy and precision ³
Detection method	The technique employed to readout the sensor (e.g. cyclic voltammetry, differential pulse voltammetry, electrochemical impedance spectroscopy)
Redox mediator/probe	A molecule that has been used in the sensing technique that possesses electroactivity and can undergo oxidation/reduction to facilitate the measurement
Sensitivity	The slope of the calibration curve for the sensor response against analyte concentration (in the case of a curve, and not a straight line, the sensitivity will be a function of analyte concentration) ⁴
Response time	The time taken from the onset of change in the cortisol concentration to when the sensor output reaches 90% of the final value ⁵
Selectivity	The extent to which other molecules (interferents/structural analogs of the analyte) interfere with the determination of the analyte according to a given procedure ⁶
Reusability	The ability of the sensor to be regenerated for multiple uses

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3. U. S. Fda, 'Bioanalytical method validation guidance for industry', *US Department of Health and Human Services Food and Drug Administration Center for Drug Evaluation and Research and Center for Veterinary Medicine*, 2018.

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Table S2: Abbreviations used in tables S3, S4, S5 and their definitions

Abbreviation	Definition	Abbreviation	Definition	Abbreviation	Definition
Sensor stack					
Ab	Antibody	GOPTS	3-glycidoxypropyltrimethoxysilane	PEDOT	poly(3,4-ethylenedioxythiophene)
Ag, AgNP	Silver, silver nanoparticle	GQD	Graphene quantum dots	PET	Poly(ethylene terephthalate)
Anti-CAb	Anti-cortisol antibody	GRP	Graphene nanoplatelets	PI	Polyimide
Apt	Aptamer	HCF	Hexacyanoferrate	PMA	1-Pyrenemethylamine hydrochloride
APTES	3-(aminopropyl)triethoxysilane	In ₂ O ₃	Indium (III) Oxide	PMF	Phenol-melamine-formaldehyde
Au, AuNP, AuNW, AuNR	Gold, gold nanoparticle, gold nanowire, gold nanorod	IDE	Interdigitated electrode	Poly(GMA-co-EGDMA)	Poly(glycidylmethacrylate-co-ethylene glycol dimethacrylate)
BSA	Bovine serum albumin	ITO	Indium tin oxide	Poly(o-PD)	Poly(o-phenylenediamine)
C	Carbon	Lg-FET	Liquid gate field effect transistor	PP	Porphyrin
CD	Cyclodextrin	MBS	3-maleimidobenzoic acid N-hydroxysuccinimide ester	PPy	Polypyrrole
CCY	Conductive carbon yarn	MCH	Mercaptohexanol	PSMA	Poly(styrene-co-methacrylic acid)
CMK-3	Ordered mesoporous carbon	MNP	Magnetic nanoparticle	PSS	Polystyrenesulfonate
CNC	Cellulose nanocrystal	MWCNT	Multi-walled carbon nanotubes	Pt	Platinum
CNT	Carbon nanotube	2ME	Mercaptoethanol	PTMS	Trimethoxy(propyl)silane
Cu	Copper	3-MPA	3-mercaptopropionic acid	PVA	Polyvinyl alcohol
d-BSA	Denatured bovine serum albumin	NHS	N-Hydroxysuccinimide	rGO	Reduced graphene oxide
DSP/DTSP	DSP/DTSP	NiNCs	Nickel Nanoclusters	SiNW	Silicon nanowire
EA	Ethanolamine	PA	Polyamide	SmM NPs	Samarian molybdate nanoparticles
EGFET	Extended gate field effect transistor	PAN	Polyacrylonitrile	SnS ₂	Tin sulphide
Fc	Ferrocene	PB	Prussian blue	SPE, SPCE	Screen-printed electrode, screen-printed carbon electrode
FET	Field effect transistor	PBASE, PBSE	1-pyrenebutyric acid N-hydroxysuccinimide ester	SWNT	Single-walled carbon nanotubes
G	Graphene	Pd	Palladium	TCPP	Tetrakis(4-carboxyphenyl) porphyrin

GA	Glutaraldehyde	PDMS	Polydimethylsiloxane	TESPSA	Triethoxysilylpropylsuccinic anhydride
GCE	Glassy carbon electrode	Pt	Platinum	TiO ₂	Titanium dioxide
				ZnO, ZnONPs, ZnONSs, ZnONRs	Zinc oxide nanoparticles, zinc oxide nanostructures, zinc oxide nanorods
Detection method					
CA	Chronoamperometry	CV	Cyclic voltammetry	DPV	Differential pulse voltammetry
EIS	Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy	I-V	Current – voltage characteristics	SWV	Square wave voltammetry
Selectivity					
AA	Ascorbic acid	EST	Estriol	NE	Norepinephrine
ALDO	Aldosterone	EtG	Ethyl Glucuronide	NPY	Neuropeptide Y
APAP	Acetaminophen	E1	Estrone	NSE	Neuron specific enolase
CA	Cholic acid	E2	B-Estradiol	17 α -OHP	17- α -hydroxyprogesterone
CL	Cholesterol	GLT	Glutamate	P	Progesterone
Cort	Cortisol	GLU	Glucose	PRDL	Prednisolone
CORT	Corticosterone	5-HT	Serotonin	PRED	Prednisone
CR	Creatinine	IL-1 β	Interleukin 1 beta	PSA	Prostate specific antigen
DHEA	Dehydroepiandrosterone	IL-6	Interleukin 6	STG	Stigmasterol
DA	Dopamine	K	Potassium	T	Testosterone
DOC	21-hydroprogesterone	LA	Lactic acid	TAC	Triamcinolone
E	Cortisone	LAC	Lactate	TYR	Tyrosine
EGFR	Epidermal growth factor receptor	MP	Methoxyprogesterone	UA	Uric acid
EPI	Epinephrine	Na	Sodium	UR	Urea

Table S3: Key information extracted for antibody-based sensors (immunosensors)

Layers in Sensor Stack					Target Biofluid	Limit of Detection (ng/mL)	Dynamic Range (ng/mL)	Electrochemical Detection Method	Redox Probe Used? (Y/N) ‡	Response Time (min)	Sensitivity	Selectivity		Regeneratable?	Validation		Reference
Substrate	Base Layer	Nanostructures	Cross linker	Blocker								Interferents tested	Worst Case Change in Electrochemical Response		Biofluid Sample: Number of Samples	Reference Analyser: Percentage Correlation/ Pearson correlation coefficient, r	
-	CCY	Fe ₂ O ₃	NR	BSA	SWT	5 x 10 ⁻⁹	1 x 10 ⁻⁶ - 1000	CV	N	2	NC	P, E, BSA, and CL (100 fg/mL) vs. Cort (100 fg/mL)	NR	NR	SWT: 3	CLIA: NR	35
-	CCY	ZnO-NRs	NR	BSA	SWT	CV: 2.5 x 10 ⁻⁷ DPV: 9.8 x 10 ⁻⁸	1 x 10 ⁻⁶ - 1000	CV & DPV	Y	15*	CV: 6.09 µA / log (g/mL) DPV: 2.12 µA / log (g/mL)	P, T, CORT, and E (100 ng/mL) vs. Cort 100 ng/mL	NR	NR	SWT: 5	CLIA: within 95% agreement	36
-	CCY	TiO ₂	NR	BSA	SWT	6 x 10 ⁻⁶	1 x 10 ⁻⁵ - 1000	CV & DPV	N	NR	CV: 2.49 µA / log (g/mL) DPV: 4.69 µA / log (g/mL)	T, P, CL, E, CORT, and BSA (100 ng/mL) vs. Cort (100 ng/mL)	± 3 µA change from the current caused by Cort	NR	SWT: 5	CLIA: NR	37
-	CCY	SnO ₂	NR	BSA	SWT	1.6 x 10 ⁻⁶	1 x 10 ⁻⁵ - 1000	CV & DPV	Y	NR	CV: -0.78 µA / log (g/mL) DPV: -4.54 µA / log (g/mL)	P, T, CORT, E, CL, GLU, UR, BSA, UA, K, Na (100 ng/mL) vs. Cort (100 ng/mL)	NR	NR	SWT: 5	CLIA: within 95% agreement	38

-	Conductive nylon thread	MXene + AuNPs	L-cys	BSA	SWT	0.54	5 - 180	CA	Y	45	0-40 ng/mL: 0.094 μ A / (cm ² ng/mL) 40-180 ng/mL: 0.015 μ A / (cm ² ng/mL)	E, CORT, AA, UA, CR (50 μ g/mL) vs. Cort	E, CORT, AA, UA, CR : <0.5 μ A Cort: ~4 μ A	NR	NR	NR	39
PDMS	NR	MWCNTs/AuNPs	NR	BSA	SWT	3 x 10 ⁻⁷	1 x 10 ⁻⁶ - 1000	DPV	Y	20*	10.85 μ A/log (g/mL)	GLU (18 μ g/mL), AA (1.8 μ g/mL), LA (93.6 mg/mL), Urea (72 μ g/mL), UA (1 ng/mL), E (91 ng/mL), and TYR (1 ng/mL) vs. Cort (10 pg/mL)	GLU, AA, LA, Urea, UA, E, TYR: <5 μ A Cort: >50 μ A	NR	SWT: 10	CLIA: within 95% agreement	16
PA	Au	ZnO	DTSP	NR	SWT	0.1	N/A	EIS	N	NR	NR	IL-6 vs. Cort (0.1 – 100 ng/mL)	NR	NR	NR	NR	60
PA	NR	ZnO	DTSP	NR	SWT	10	10 - 200	EIS	N	NR	NR	IL-6	< 20% (SST) Cort: 20-80%	NR	NR	NR	65
PA	ZnO	NR	DTSP	NR	SWT	1	10 - 200	EIS	N	15*	NR	IL-1 β vs. Cort (1 pg/mL – 100 ng/mL)	IL-1 β : <6.2 % Cort: 19.5 – 50%	NR	NR	NR	62
PA	Pd	MoS ₂	DTSP	NR	SWT	1	1 - 500	EIS	N	7*	NR	EtG vs. Cort (1-500 ng/mL)	EtG: <20 % (LOB) Cort: 25 – 45%	NR	NR	NR	44
PI	G	AuNPs	DTSP	EA	SWT	0.0036	0.0036 - 36.25	CA	Y	30*	0.46 μ A/ log (pM)	AA, UA, GLU (1mM)	NR	N	NR	NR	40
Paper	C	GO	APTES / Protein A	NR	SWT	NR	0.1 - 150	CV	Y	NR	NR	NR	NR	NR	NR	NR	47
FET	ITO-PET	NR	PSMA	NR	SWT	1	1 x 10 ⁻⁵ - 10	I-V	N	NR	0.3%/ decade (g/mL)	17 α -OHP vs. Cort (1 fg/mL - 10 ng/mL)	17 α -OHP: <1.5% Cort: >2%	N	NR	NR	55

FET (Flexible foil)	Sensing part: Au Amplification part: PEDOT : PSS	NR	3-MPA	NR	SWT	0.036	0.36 - 362.5	I-V & EIS	N	5	50 μ A/dec	NR	NR	NR	SWT: 8	LC-MS/MS: r = 0.83	58
FET	NR	SWCNTs + AuNPs	NR	NR	SWT	SWCNTs: 3.63×10^{-6} SWCNTs + AuNPs: 3.63×10^{-5}	0.0001 - 79.75	I-V	N	NR	SWCNTs: 0.055 mS/ log (M) SWCNTs + AuNPs: -0.016 mS/log (M)	NR	NR	NR	NR	NR	59
ITO	PEDOT :PSS	Poly(EDOT-COOH-co-EDOT-E3G)	NR	NR	SWT	8.8×10^{-9}	1×10^{-6} - 1000	I-V	N	10s	NR	CL, CORT, PRDL, E (2 μ g/mL) vs. Cort (100 ng/mL)	NR	NR	NR	NR	46
AlGaIn/GaN HEMT	Au	NR	DTSP	EA	SLV	4×10^{-4}	4×10^{-4} - 3.6×10^{-1}	I-V	N	NR	NR	E, CORT, and P (10 pM) vs. Cort (10 pM)	< 25% relative to the response of cortisol	NR	NR	NR	52
IDE	Au	NR	DTSP	EA	SLV	0.01	0.01 - 100	CV	Y	30*	6 μ A/ (pg/mL)	PSA, NSE, EGFR, BSA+Cort (100 pg/mL) and Cort 100 pg/mL	PSA, NSE, EGFR, BSA+Cort: 1-2% Cort: 13-14%	NR	SLV: 8	ELISA: 95 - 98%	3
Si	Au	ZnO-NPs	NR	BSA	SLV	4×10^{-4}	N/A	CV	Y	30*	ZnNRs: 11.86 μ A/ log (M) ZnNFs: 7.74 μ A/log (M)	PSA, NSE, EGFR, BSA+Cort (100 pg/mL) vs. Cort (100 pg/mL)	PSA, NSE, EGFR, BSA+Cort: ~1-3% Cort: ~15%	NR	SLV: NR	ELISA: NR	41

Paper	Au	GRP-Polymer	DTSP	BSA	SLV	$8.7 \times 10^{-4} \pm 1.2 \times 10^{-4}$	0.001 - 10	EIS	N	12	NR	AA (1 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$) vs. Cort (1 ng/mL)	AA: < 50 Ω Cort: > 225 Ω	NR	SLV: 7	ELISA: 96.3%	5
Paper	Au	GRP-Polymer	DTSP	EA	SLV	0.003	0.003 - 10,000	EIS	N	12	50 $\Omega/(\text{pg}/\text{mL})$	NR	NR	NR	SLV: NR	ELISA: NR	61
-	Au	SWNT	PMA/Cort-NHS	Tween-20 and MCH	SLV	0.001	0.001-10	I-V	N	10*	14.9%/(ng/mL)	DOC vs. Cort (1 pg/mL - 1 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$)	No decrease in normalized resistance unlike cortisol	NR	NR	NR	57
-	ITO	rGO	NR	EA	SLV	0.01	1 - 10	I-V	N	NR	NR	NR	NR	NR	Buffer solution of rat adrenal slices	ELISA: NR	53
-	ITO	NR	NR	NR	SLV	1.03×10^{-3}	0 - 50	CV & SWV	Y [€]	35	0.10 $\mu\text{A} / \log(\text{ng}/\text{mL})$	NR	NR	NR	NR	NR	51
-	GCE	SnS ₂	NR	BSA	SLV	0.0363	0.0363 - 36250	CV & DPV	Y	NR	0.0103 mA / Mcm^2	E2, T, P, and CORT (100 nM) vs. Cort (10 nM)	<5% than that of cortisol	NR	SLV: 2	ELISA: 95 - 98%	43
Quartz	rGO	NR	d-BSA	d-BSA	SLV	0.0036	0.036 - 36.25	EIS	N	30*	9.61% / log (mol/L)	ALDO and P (10 nM) vs. Cort (NR)	ALDO: 5.5% P: 6.2% Cort: >45%	NR	NR	NR	64
SiO ₂	Au	NR	NR	NR	SER	5	10 - 150	EIS	N	10	0.0066/ ($\mu\text{g}/\text{dL}$)	IL-6 and T (NR)	NR	NR	SER: 65	ELISA: NR	63
EGFET	GRP	GRP	PBASE	EA	SER	8.5×10^{-4}	0.001 - 10	I-V	N	30*	72.30 $\mu\text{A} / \log(\text{g}/\text{mL})$	P, E, and CORT (10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$) vs. Cort (10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$)	P: 0.10 V, E: 0.22 V, CORT: 0.27 V Cort: 0.61 V	NR	NR	NR	54

IDE	Au	NR	DTSP	EA	NR	0.01	0.0036 – 36.25	CV	Y	30*	0.207 μ A/M	PSA, NSE, and EGFR (100 pg/mL)	~3-5%	N	NR	NR	50
IDE	NR	AgNPs	GOPTS	EA	NR	0.01	N/A	Current change	N	30*	0.057 μ A / (ng/mL)	NE and P (100 ng/mL)	NR	NR	NR	NR	68
Si	Au	ZnO-NSs		BSA	NR	4 x 10 ⁻⁴	N/A	EIS	Y	30*	ZnNRs : 3.078 K Ω /log (M) ZnNFs : 540 Ω /log (M)	NR	NR	NR	NR	NR	42
FET	Au	PPy NT	APTES		NR	0.1	0.1 – 97.88	I-V	N	<5s	NR	E, CORT, and PRDL (2 μ M) vs. Cort (270 pM)	E, CORT, PDRL: <0.5 % Cort: ~ 3%	NR	N μ R	NR	45
G-EGFET	NR	G	PBASE	EA	N/A	N/A	N/A	I-V	N	NR	NR	NR	NR	NR	NR	NR	56
-	PMF	Cu-rGO	NR	NR	NR	NR	10 - 500	I-V (chemiresistive)	N	5	2.81 Ω / (μ g/dL)	NR	NR	NR	NR	NR	66

SWT: Sweat, SLV: Saliva, and SER: Serum, NR: Not reported, NC: Not clear, LOB: Limit of Blank

Notes:

Normal cortisol levels in (i) blood and serum: 20 – 250 ng/mL, (ii) saliva: 1 – 8 ng/mL, and (iii) sweat: 8 – 141 ng/mL.

* Incubation time, where this was not explicitly declared as the sensor's response time. This was done following the common practice in which most papers reported the incubation time as the response time since the measurement itself usually takes only a few seconds.

¥ If redox probed used? was yes (Y), potassium ferricyanide/ferrocyanide complex [Fe(CN)₆]^{3-/4-} was used as the redox probe

€ Antibody was tagged with the redox probe ferrocene (Ab-Fc)

Supplementary Table S4: Key information extracted for MIP-based sensors

Layers in Sensor Stack				Target Biofluid	Limit of Detection (ng/mL)	Dynamic Range (ng/mL)	Electrochemical Detection Method	Redox Probe Used? (Y/N) [‡]	Response Time (min)	Sensitivity	Selectivity		Regeneratable?	Validation in Biofluid		Reference
Substrate	Base Layer	Nanostructures	MIP Film								Interferents tested	Worst Case Change in Electrochemical Response		Number of Samples	Reference Analyser: Percentage Correlation/ Pearson correlation coefficient, r	
PDMS	NR	AgNPs/CNC-CNT	Poly(GMA-co-EGDMA)	SWT	2 ± 0.4	10 - 66	CV	N	3	1.87 / (ng/mL)	GLU, EPI, E2, MP (100 ng/mL) vs. Cort (10 ng/mL)	NR	Y (10 times)	NC	HPLC-UV: agrees to within 5% with the sensor	18
PET	C	NR	PPy-PB	SWT	PBS: 0.3263 AS: 0.0725	0.33 - 3625	CA	Y [#]	3.5	PBS: 38.8 nA/ log (nM) AS: 60.31 nA/ log (nM)	GLU (50 µM), LAC (5mM), UR (5mM), AA (50 µm), APAP (50 µm), and UA (50 µm) vs. Cort (1 µM)	NR	N	SWT: 10	ELISA: NR	20
PET	C	NR	PPy-PB	SWT	0.16	0.1 - 10000	CA	Y [#]	3	-6 ± 0.2 nA/ log (ng/mL)	PRDL, E, CORT (100 ng/mL), GLU (100 µM), LA (30 mM) vs Cort (100 ng/mL)	PRDL, E, CORT, GLU, LA : 20, 8, 22, 15, 2 nA Cort: 63 nA	N	NR	NR	23
Textile	PANI/CNC-CNT	AuNPs	Poly(GMA-co-EGDMA)	SWT	8	9.8 - 49.5	CV	N	2		LAC, AA, EST (45 ng/mL) vs. Cort (45 ng/mL)	LAC, AA, EST: 0.02 ± 0.001 µF Cort: 0.087 ± 0.008 µF	Y (15 times)	NR	NR	19

SPCE	NR	NR	PPy	SLV	4 x 10 ⁻⁴	4 x 10 ⁻⁴ - 3625	CV	Y	15*	NR	P, PRDL, and LAC (100 nM) + Cort (100 nM)	P: 11.4%, PRDL: 18.3% LAC: 1.5%	Y (7 times)	SLV: 5	ELISA: NR	21
-	GCE	CD-rGO	PPy-HCF	SLV	0.007	0.005 - 5000	CV	Y - HCF	10	8.81 μA / log (ng/mL) cm ²	T, P, GLU, LAC, CL, UR (100 ng/mL) and Cort (5 ng/mL) relative to blank	P: ~0.22, T, GLU, LAC, CL, UR: <0.2 Cort: >0.4	NR	NR	NR	26
-	GCE	AuNPs	Poly(o-PD)	SLV	1 x 10 ⁻⁴	4 x 10 ⁻⁴ - 181.25	CV, SWV, EIS	Y	8	2.06 μA/ log (M)	DHEA, P, E2, EST, E1 (10 nM), GLU, 5-HT, DA, AA (100 nM) vs. Cort (10 nM)	DHEA, P, E2, EST, E1, GLU, 5-HT, DA, AA: < 2μA Cort:>10 μA	Y (3 times)	NR	NR	25
-	GCE	NiNCs/ Nitrogen-doped CNTs	Poly(o-PD)	SLV	8.60 x 10 ⁻⁷	3.63 x 10 ⁻⁶ - 0.3625	DPV	Y	NR	7.13 μA/ log (M)	T, PRED, E1, STG, GLT, UA, GLU (10 ⁻¹⁰ M) vs. Cort (10 ⁻¹⁰ M)	T, PRED, E1, STG, GLT, UA, GLU: <10 μA Cort:35 μA	NR	NR	NR	22
SPCE	NR	NR	PPy	NR	0.0036	NR	DPV	Y	15	9.47 μA/log C	LAC (5 mM), GLU, AA, UA, APEP, UR (50 μM) vs Cort (1 nM)	NR	NR	NR	NR	24

SWT: Sweat, SLV: Saliva, and SER: Serum, NR: Not reported, NC: Not clear

Notes:

Normal cortisol levels in (i) blood and serum: 20 – 250 ng/mL, (ii) saliva: 1 – 8 ng/mL, and (iii) sweat: 8 – 141 ng/mL.

*Incubation time where this was not explicitly declared as the sensor's response time. This was done following the common practice in which most papers reported the incubation time as the response time since the measurement itself usually takes seconds.

¥ If redox probed used? was yes (Y), potassium ferricyanide/ferrocyanide complex [Fe(CN)₆]^{3-/4-} was used as the redox probe

Redox probe Prussian blue (PB) was embedded in the MIP film

Table S5: Key information extracted for aptamer-based sensors (aptasensors)

Layers in Sensor Stack					Target Biofluid	LOD (ng/mL)	Dynamic Range (ng/mL)	Electrochemical Detection Method	Redox Probe Used? (Y/N)*	Response Time (min)	Sensitivity	Selectivity		Regeneratable?	Validation		Reference
Substrate	Base Layer	Nanostructures	Cross linker or Silane or Functionality Attached to Aptamer	Blocker								Interferents tested	Worst Case Change in Electrochemical Response		Biofluid Sample : Number of Samples	Reference Analyser: Percentage Correlation/ Pearson correlation coefficient, r	
PA	-	ZnO	SH-Apt	NR	SWT	4	1 -256	EIS	N	5*	13.57%/log (ng/mL)	PRED (2-256 ng/mL) D, DHEA, and NPY (NR)	PRED: <SST (<20%) Cort: 20-50% DHEA, NPY: ~-20% Cort: ~40%	NR	NR	NR	4
PA	-	ZnO	SH-Apt	NR	SWT	1	1 - 256	EIS	N	NR	NR	P, DHEA, and PRDL (200 ng/mL) vs. Cort (200 ng/mL)	P, DHEA, PRDL: <3% Cort: >25%	NR	SWT: 9	LUMINEX: r = 0.97	69
PI (FET)	In ₂ O ₃	NR	SH-Apt + APTES + PTMS + MBS	NR	SWT	4 x 10 ⁻⁴	4 x 10 ⁻⁴ - 362.5	I-V	N	NR	NR	P (200 pM), T (400 pM), 5-HT (10 nM) vs. Cort (10 nM)	NR	NR	SLV: 4 SWT: 4	ELISA: r=0.98 SWT: r=0.87	78
PET (FET)	Au	PEDOT-PAN NFs	Amino -Apt	NR	SWT & SLV	0.0036	0.004 - 3625	I-V	N	<5s	NR	CORT, 5-HT, NE, DA, PRDL, E (100 nM) vs. Cort (10 pM)	CORT, 5-HT, NE, DA, PRDL, E: ~0% Cort: ~0.2%	NR	SWT: 6	ELISA: NR	77

Au	NR	AuNW-BSA-GA	SH-Apt	2ME	SER	0.25	0.36 - 362	DPV	Y [£]	30*	78.0 nA/mm ² / (nM)	EPI, CA, and GLU (1000 nM)	< 10% than that of Cort	Y (3 times)	Spiked Cort	Absorbance & Fluorescence Spectroscopies: NR	72
Au	NR	NR	SH-Apt	MC H	SER	Buffer: 1.5	Buffer: 0.1 - 750	DPV	Y [£]	NR	Buffer: 0.17 μ A / (ng/mL) 50% SER: 0.66 μ A / (ng/mL)	E2 (400 pg/mL), P (1 μ g/mL), T (0.01 μ g/mL) vs. Cort (0.06 μ g/mL)	E2, T: ~ 0% P: 18%	NR	SER: 5	Immunoassay: NR	67
IDE	NR	GNR-Apt	SH-Apt + APTES	EA	SER	0.01	NR	CA	N	30*	22 μ A / log (ng/mL)	NE and P (1 μ g/mL) vs. Cort (1 μ g/mL)	20-fold for Cort	NR	NR	NR	73
SPE	NR	GQD	NR	NR	NR	1 x 10 ⁻⁴	1 x 10 ⁻⁴ - 100	CV	Y	15	2.1 μ A/log (pg/mL)	CORT, TAC, and E (NR)	30.35%, 2.615%, and 3.585% w.r.t Cort	NR	NR	NR	74
EG-FET	Pt	G	PBSE	NR	NR	0.073	0.36 - 3625	I-V	N	30*	14 mV/decade	T (10 pM – 10 nM) and E (1 nM – 10 μ M)	NR	NR	NR	NR	81, 82
Au	NR	NR	SH-Apt	MC H	NR	0.05	0.05 - 100	SWV	Y [£]	15*	0.079 μ A / (ng/mL)	P, E2, T, GLU (0.5 ng/mL) vs. Cort (0.05 ng/mL)	P, E2, T, GLU : 32, 16, 21, 10%	Y (5 times)	NR	NR	79

SWT: Sweat, SLV: Saliva, and SER: Serum, NR: Not reported, NC: Not clear, SH-Apt: Thiolated aptamer, Amino-Apt: Amino-modified aptamer

Notes:

Normal cortisol levels in (i) blood and serum: 20 – 250 ng/mL, (ii) saliva: 1 – 8 ng/mL, and (iii) sweat: 8 – 141 ng/mL.

* Incubation time where this was not explicitly declared as the sensor's response time. This was done following the common practice in which most papers reported the incubation time as the response time since the measurement itself usually takes seconds.

¥ If redox probed used? was yes (Y), potassium ferricyanide/ferrocyanide complex [Fe(CN)₆]^{3-/4-} was used as the redox probe

£ Aptamer was modified with the redox probe methylene blue (MB)

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